

NOVEL GREEN DESIGN OF ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES SYNTHESIS USING CASSIA TORA PLANT EXTRACT AND THEIR ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract:

Our study involves the Eco compatible design for the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles using Cassia tora leaves extract. No harmful toxic chemicals were used in the synthesis. The synthesized ZnO nanoparticles has applications in drug delivery studies. The synthesized nanoparticles are quite stable under room temperature and are prepared in the laboratory using reduction method using leaves extract of Cassia tora. The synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles were characterized by UV- Visible spectrometry, DLS (dynamic light scattering) and FT-IR. DLS data revealed that the average size of synthesized nanoparticle is 55 nm. The zinc oxide nanoparticles also showed good antibacterial activity against different bacterial strains.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanomaterials of diameters ranging from 1 to 100 nm are created, altered, and imaged in the field of nanotechnology (S. Alharbim et al., 2022). Particles with sizes between those of a microscopy and a mesoscopic are called nanoparticles. The bacterium, with higher surface area to volume ratio and higher fraction of surface molecules, is enormous in comparison to the dimensions of nanoparticles containing other "small" molecules. At the nanoscale, they possess distinct physicochemical characteristics, including optical, magnetic, catalytic, and antibacterproperties (Beyene H. D. et al., 2017).

Among the significant fields include applications in food, cosmetics, environment, optoelectronics, chemical industries, catalysts, energy science, drug delivery and in biomedical sciences.

Uses of nanoparticles has been reported in ranges of industries (Ebrahimzadeh et al., 2020).

The nanomaterials have been proved to have larger surface areas over conventional methods. Furthermore, they have unique physical and chemical characteristics not generally found in non-nano metals such as interface effect and quantum impacts (S. Yinget al., 2022). Nanoparticles have unique features such as their small sizes, large surface area, free hanging bonds and superior reactivity (1, 2) thus attracting exponential growth of global investments and research.

Biological method involving greener designs for promised to be alternative, cost-effective and environmentally sound method (4, 5). These design further give valuable insights into various reports emphasize that plant based nanoparticles had valuable impact in agriculture, pharmaceuticals, drug delivery and production of other commercial applications (3). Plant extracts mediated synthesis of nanoparticles generally exploit their uses as (6) natural reducing, capping and stabilizing agents (7, 8). This further minimizes dependency on the chemicals with higher toxicity (9-12). Recently, plants and their extracts based nanoparticles synthesis gained attraction because of their ease availability and mass production (13). Zinc oxide nanoparticles have been reported even by the Romans in 2,000 BC. Most recently ZnO has been used as a semiconductor material. Nanomaterial synthesis involves the principles of nanotechnology. The term nanomaterial is defined by various organization in different manner (M. Bachhav et. Al., 2015).

In order to exploit the antibacterial properties of Zinc oxide nanoparticles they have been used to control bacterial infection of septic wounds, many conventional antibiotics have been tested by researcher to maintain sterile conditions on wounds, and possibly enhance their healing rate. However, overconsumption of antibiotics have been reported to lead to mutations in DNA, transposons, and R-Plasmids of bacteria which may further result in the development of drug resistance (Melaiyekn et. al., 2005). Prolonged antibiotic administration may inhibit the growth of natural flora, growth factors and cytokines. Polymeric particles made of synthetic or natural polymers, known as nanoparticles, are spherical in shape. Their sizes vary from 10 to

500 nm. These particles offer a wide range of possible uses due to their spherical form and excellent surface area to volume ratio (Berry & Curtis, 2003). Rapid advancements in nanoparticle technology have made it possible promising toll to treat a wide range of neurological conditions like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases (Emerich & Thanos, 2003). Delivering medications to the brain is still limited owing to the blood-brain barrier's (BBB) limitations. This barrier, which is primarily made up of endothelial cells connected by tight junctions in their outer membranes, restricts the movement of molecules across it by limiting molecular exchange to transcellular transport.

Fig.1 Nanoparticles labeled Infographic

Physical and chemical behaviors of zinc oxide nanoparticle can be easily modified by changing their morphology adopting different synthetic routes and using different precursors (Bala et al., 2015). These are the inorganic compounds of group II–IV semiconductor for analytical sensing applications (Matinise et al., 2017). Zinc oxide nanoparticle are water insoluble white powder and has an energy band of 3.37 eV and a bonding energy of 60 meV, which provides its excellent chemical, electrical, and thermal stabilities (Watanabe, 2018). Zinc oxide nanoparticle also shows excellent optical, electrical, and photocatalytic properties (Kumar et al., 2014) and

thus finds applications in solar cells, photo catalysis, and chemical sensor (NaveedUl Haq et al., 2017). Recently, ZnO nanoparticles are used to form nanowires, nanofibers and also in applications involving photovoltaic systems and in biomedical fields. Green chemistry designs has been strongly presented recently in the scientific arena as worldwide investigations have been held on subjects involving bacteria, fungus, oralgae-based synthesis.

Fig. 2 Synthesis of Nanoparticles under different conditions

Green synthetic designs intended to eliminate toxic waste, reduce energy consumption and to use eco-friendly methods of synthesis minimizing dependency on chemicals. This also targets innovative scientific solutions to solve environmental issues in laboratory.

These designs have become a new and promising field of research in recent years being simple, cost-effective techniques also nanoparticles formed by these techniques have good stability, less time consumption, non-toxic by-products, environment-friendly and can be easily scaled up for large-scale synthesis.

Fig. 3 Highlights of Green Synthesis

These methods have advantages over traditional Chemical synthesis methods which involves use of toxic chemical species adsorbed on the surface of nanoparticles. Green metal nanoparticle synthetic approaches are more reliable and economic route to synthesize. This research aims to explain the advantages of various types of biomolecules as reliable, sustainable, and eco- friendly components for synthesizing Zinc metal oxide nanoparticles.

Table.1 Various green nanoparticles synthesized using plant parts

S.NO	Leaf component	Compound	Application	Reference no.
1.	Raphanus sativus.	Zinc Oxide nanoparticle	Anticancer property.	61
2.	Cassia Tora	Silver nanoparticle	Antioxidant and antibacterial activities.	15
3.	Myristicafragrans	(ZnO)Nanoparticles	Biological and Environmental	59

4.	Cassia fistula	(ZnO) nanoparticles	Photo degradative, antioxidant and antibacterial activities	10
5.	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i> L.	zinc oxide nanoparticles	multiple in vitro biological	3
7.	Pisonia Alba	zinc oxide nanoparticles	antibacterial activity	9
8.	Alovera	Au nanoparticles	biological synthesis	63
9.	Argemone maxicana	Ag	antimicrobial activities	68
10.	Syzygium cumini	Ag	antimicrobial activities	69
12.	Sorghum spp.	Ag	Environment al remediation and treatment of hazardous waste	70
13	Curcuma longa	Ag	bactericidal activity	71
14	Allium cepa	Ag	antibacterial activity	72
15	Mentha piperita	Ag	antimicrobial activity against clinically isolated pathogens	73
16	Syzygium cumini	Ag	antioxidant activities	74
17	Memecylon edule	Ag	Environment AL remediation and treatment of hazardous waste	75
18	Murraya keenigii	Ag	biosynthesis	76

19	Mangifera indica	Ag	antibacterial effect	77
20	Nicotiana tobaccum	Ag	evaluation of their antimicrobial efficacy	78
21	Cyymbopogon flexuosus	Au	Biological synthesis	51
22	Pelargonium graveolens	Au	Bio reduction	53
23	Emblica officinalis	Au	Biological synthesis	56
24	Tanacetum vulgare	Au	Biochemical	66
25	Menta piperita	Au	antimicrobial activity against clinically isolated pathogens	73
26	Memecylon edule	Au	mediated green synthesis	75
27	Murraya keenigii	Au	Bio reduction	76
28	Cicer arietinum	Au	green biogenic	86
29	Camellia sinensis	Au	bio matrix-embedded	87
30	Coriandum sativum	Au	biosynthesis	88
31	Eucalyptus camaldulensis	Au	Biochemical	89
32	Pelargonium, roseum	Au	Biochemical	89
33	Azadirachta indica	Au	biosynthesis	89
34	Psidium guajava	Au	antiamlignant	90
35	Cinnamomum zeylanicum	Au	Spectrochim	91
36	Magnolia kobus,	Au	Biochemical	92
37	Diopyrus kaki	Au	Biochemical	92
38	Terminalia catappa	Au	Spectrochim	93
39	Stevia rebaudiana	Au	Stevia rebaudiana	94
40	Mangifera indica	Au	Spectrochim	95

2.1 Materials

S.No	Chemical compound	Chemical formula	Molecular weight
1.	Zinc nitrate hex hydrate	Zn (NO ₃) ₃ 6H ₂ O	189.36 g/mol

2.2 Glassware's.

- ❖ Beaker- Borosil beaker of 100ml, 50ml 25ml were used in experiment.
- ❖ Micropipette- 1 to 100 ml were employed for taking variable amount of liquid.
- ❖ Measuring cylinder-Measuring cylinder of 10ml, and 100ml were used to measure the volume of liquids.
- ❖ Funnel

2.3 Plant collection

Cassia Tora leaves were sourced from village Baroda kutharood forests of Raipur Baloda Bazar Districts. India. The leaves were handpicked and shade dried and after pulverization were passed through 100 pore size mesh and finally powdered and stored in air tight glass jars for further experimentation.

2.4 Preparation of the extract

The dried leaves were finely powdered with a grinder and further subjected to Soxhlet apparatus using various polar and non polar solvent. Each round bottom flask has 50 ml of methanol, the evaporator was run at 100 C for 15 min, The plant extract is now ready to be stored in airtight bottles at 4 C.

3.1 Experiment:

Synthesis of ZnONPs

In this research ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized by eco-friendly green route of incorporating *C. fistula* leaf extract [28, 29]. Zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Zn (NO₃)₃ 6H₂O) was procured from Sigma Aldrich (AR) and used without further purification. Stoichiometric amount of the salt was dissolved with 0.2 g of *C. fistula* leaf extract in 10 ml of distilled water.

The mixture was kept in a pre-heated muffle furnace initially at 400 °C and later at 710 °C. A fine milky white colored material was obtained after completion of reaction after 5 mins. The synthesis of nano particles was repeated with different concentrations of the plant extract such as 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 and 0.6 g. The obtained product was stored in airtight container for further use.

Fig. 4 Graphical Representation of our Green approach

Characterization of ZnONPs

The synthesized ZnO nanoparticles were characterized using UV absorption spectra and photoluminescence. UV absorbance peaks for zinc oxide nanoparticles were observed at 348 nm. UV-Visible spectroscopic characterization of biosynthesized ZnO-NPs were done between range between 200 nm to 700 nm. For UV–Visible spectroscopy, the resultant pellet formed from each of the reaction mixture were re-suspended in distilled water and spectrum scans were performed using Systronics Double Beam Spectrophotometer (Model 2202, Systronics Ltd.) in diffuse reflectance mode using Zinc nitrate as reference material. UV absorbance peaks for zinc oxide nanoparticles were observed between 348nm from plant extract of Cassia Tora.

Fig5. UV-visible spectra of ZnO nanoparticles prepared with various concentration of Cassia Tora leafextract.

3.2 DLS Zeta Size

The Z-potential of the aqueous preparation of ZnO-NPs in distilled water (DW) was measured to be -33.04mV , and this can thus it is found to be strongly anionic. The hydrodynamic size of the particles as determined using dynamic light scattering microscopy and was found to be 55 nm.

Fig 6 .Size of nanoparticle synthesized (d.nm)

Fig. 7 Zeta Potential (mv) measurement of the nanoparticle

3.3 FTIR Spectroscopy:

The study of the therapeutic effects of *Cassia tora* the macroscopic fingerprint region of FTIR peaks were used and revealed the presence of a variety of functional groups that were very important to determine the origin of different extracts and the identity of medicinal ingredients. The plant included functional groups of several phytochemicals, including 3400 which corresponds to CH, C-OH, CH₂-OCH₃/CH₂-CH₃ and OH functional groups present in the alkaloids, 2900 is assisted to C-N stretching of amine group, 1600 due hydroxyl (O-H) group of H₂O [39]. Peak at 1450 may be assigned to the symmetric stretching of the carboxyl region of the amino acid residues of the protein molecules [27], 1050 signified amide III band of the random coil of protein [26].

Fig 8: FTIR Spectra of Zinc nanoparticles synthesized by Cassia tora life extract data.

3.4 Antibacterial Activity

The varying concentrations (0.01%, 0.015%, 0.02%, 0.025%, 0.03%) of ZnO nanoparticles were employed to determine the ideal concentration to inhibit the growth of bacteria.

The method of antibacterial test is Bio chemical method. To evaluate the antimicrobial efficacy of these nanoparticles opposed to the general E. coli and E. coli O157:H7, in LB broth, the optical density (OD) was assessed both with and without nanoparticles. ZnO nanoparticle levels of 25.0 or 50.0 µg/ml , completely stopped the general growth of *E.coli* during the incubation period of 24 hours. There was just a little inhibition at 10.0 µg/ml.

S.no	Concentration(mg/ml) ZnONPs	Zone of inhibition(nm) E.Coli
1.	25	7
2.	50	10

Fig.9 Antibacterial Activity

4.1 Conclusion

In the study, a simple, environmentally friendly green design has been incorporated for novel nanoparticle synthesis. This design has many advantages over traditional chemical methods as the phytofabrication of zinc oxide nanoparticle by using leaves extract of Cassia Tora. Stable

Zinc oxide nanoparticles are formed extracellularly when metal ions are reduced using plant extracts. The synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles were characterized by UV- Visible spectroscopy, DLS (dynamic light scattering) and FT-IR techniques. DLS data revealed that the average size of synthesized nanoparticle is 55 nm. The zinc oxide nanoparticles also showed good antibacterial activity against different strains and showed the presence of phytochemicals which pose antibacterial properties.

4.2 REFERENCES

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